

Abbreviation

		HT	high tariff
BSM	bill sharing method	KOR	keys of repartition
CC	community cooperatives	LT	low tariff
		P2P	peer-to-peer
CEC	citizen energy community	PEB	positive energy building
CSC	collective self-consumption	PEC	positive energy community
DR	demand response	PP	payback period
DSO	distribution system operator	PV	photovoltaic
ES	energy storage	REC	renewable energy community
ESCO	energy serving company	RES	renewable energy sources
EU	European Union	TSO	transmission system operator
EV	electric vehicle		
FiT	feed-in-tariff	VAT	value added tax

Graphical abstract

Highlights

Energy Sharing: Encouraging Citizen Participation in Energy Communities and Collective Self-Consumption

- Recommendation of the most beneficial net-metering approach for diverse types of communities
- Economic analysis of collective self-consumption with different keys of repartition for energy sharing
- Proposal of a business customer – household energy community
- Analysis and recommendation of sharing cost design between energy community members
- Recommendation on RES incentives deduction for shared energy between community members

Energy Sharing: Encouraging Citizen Participation in Energy Communities and Collective Self-Consumption

Abstract

To empower the citizens' engagement in the low-carbon transition, European directives highlight the importance of the local energy-sharing concept. This can be achieved with renewable energy communities (REC), citizen energy communities (CEC), collective self-consumption (CSC), peer-to-peer trading, energy cooperatives, etc. To investigate the potential benefits of local energy sharing in Croatia, this research focused on financial analyses and return of investment calculation for local photovoltaic (PV) systems based on real load and PV measurement data. Due to a limited number of energy community projects in Croatia and poorly defined regulations, the goal was to provide insight into different types of possible community trading approaches: household collective-self consumption with joint investment in PV, an energy community with only business customers, and a household-business customer energy community. Comprehensive financial analyses are based on the existing regulatory framework in Croatia with two different net-metering approaches for final customers with the onsite PV generation. The results suggest the selection of the most beneficial net-metering approach for different types of communities: monthly net metering is more beneficial for household CSC and energy communities with only business customers, while 15-minute net metering results in lower costs and shorter return of investment period for a household-business customer energy community. Moreover, CSC analyses are made based on static, annual, and monthly keys of repartition (KoR) for energy sharing. Analyses show that electricity bills differ under the proposed KoR due to diverse consumption profiles. Consumers with high monthly consumption have the highest electricity bill with static KoR due to equal distribution of produced energy between all community members, while with annual or monthly KoR their electricity bill significantly decreases because they are allocated more PV production. Several settlement options are proposed highlighting the need for more detailed regulation and suggesting some regulation changes that will lead to higher acceptance of energy com-

munities and joint local investments, such as the deduction of RES incentives for shared energy. Furthermore, the analyses suggest that regulation should define how excess PV production is shared and remunerated after the application of KoR in the second stage. Even though the analyses demonstrate the Croatian case study, the results and conclusions can easily be translated to any European country without a clear and detailed regulatory framework for energy communities.

Keywords: Collective-self consumption, Energy communities, Keys of repartition for energy sharing, Local energy sharing

1. Introduction

Mitigating climate change has been set very high on the European Union (EU) priority list. To keep the temperature increase below 2°C compared to the pre-industrialized period, some major challenges have been addressed over the last decades. Reduction of greenhouse gas emissions together with the massive integration of renewable energy sources (RES) are seen as the leading actions in achieving carbon neutrality by 2050 [1]. Moreover, the EU initiates citizen-based actions and projects to increase public awareness of their important role in the transition towards a clean and green power system. Higher acceptance of RES and other low-carbon technologies leads to more private investments which will open the door for providing diverse benefits to all involved participants, such as a reduction in electricity bills for citizens, increasing energy efficiency, load management, and providing flexibility services to the system operator. Public involvement can be achieved through different actions, such as aggregation, investments, or diverse forms of collective energy actions (energy communities, peer-to-peer (P2P) trading, community or collective self-consumption (CSC), transactive energy, energy cooperatives, community prosumerism, local energy markets, community collective generation, third-party-sponsored communities, community flexibility aggregation, community energy service company (ESCO), e-mobility cooperatives).

In the first part of the paper, an analysis of the current situation in EU member states has been conducted to identify best practices that can be applied in the Croatian context. This analysis provides an overview of the energy-sharing models and solutions implemented in the EU, serving as a foundation for the second part of the paper, which includes calculations and

financial analyses focused on energy sharing within Croatian energy communities, as well as existing individual models for households and businesses in Croatia that use different energy billing methods, in line with current Croatian legislation. Particular emphasis is placed on different models for sharing and billing energy, as well as the potential for reducing grid fees, reflecting best practices observed across the EU.

1.1. Literature review

The literature review is focused on the review papers, scientific research, and project deliverables investigating the real-life implementation of energy communities and local energy-sharing projects led by citizens.

Review papers focused on different aspects of energy communities are summarized in the Table 1.

1.1.1. Energy communities and local energy sharing in scientific research

A credit calculation model in Finland [16], representing a virtual net-metering in multi-dwelling buildings by distributing surplus solar electricity among shareholders according to a declared ratio, significantly improves return period and self-consumption ratio. While this approach relies on fixed distribution rules, the authors in [17] propose four algorithms for dynamic sharing keys based on participants' contributions to the community: a consumption proportional key, a Pearson correlation coefficient-based key to evaluate synchronism between electricity drawn from the grid and the surplus fed into the grid, a trend-based key that accounts for the difference between purchased and injected energy, and a combination of the previous two keys. The results show that all keys except the first one lean to attribute a greater amount of energy uniformly among community members. On the other hand, consumers with the highest annual consumptions are those most rewarded by the first key.

Four regulation variants in collective-self consumption exploring the impact of different surplus remuneration levels were investigated in [18]: full exemption of tax and grid tariff, no exemption, reduced surplus remuneration, and lower selling price for collective self-consumption electricity. The results show generally similar choices of low-carbon technologies under the different collective-self consumption frameworks, with the largest differences in the magnitude and distribution of benefits with the PV system. Authors in [19] analyzed self-consumption ratios and economic savings in collective-self consumption example in France based on three KoR: static, default dy-

Table 1: Review papers on energy communities

Reference	Focus of the paper
[2]	Strengths, benefits, and shortcomings of local energy sharing
[3]	Systematization of local energy market models
[4], [5]	Identification of social aspects in energy community trading
[6]	Overview of meaning, activities, and objectives in the energy system communities
[7]	Connection between community participation and mini-grid projects
[8]	Cost allocation in integrated community energy systems based on the tariff design objectives and regulatory principles
[9]	Comparison of 36 energy communities identifying their business models, key activities, motivations, governance, ownership, and operation
[10]	Energy community business models in England
[11]	Classification of papers based on three market designs: full P2P market, community-based market, and hybrid P2P market
[12]	Comparison of positive energy building (PEB) and positive energy community (PEC)
[13]	Challenges and barriers in the PV energy community from the final user's side including policy-related, economical, technical, and social aspects
[14], [15]	Applications, challenges, and opportunities of blockchain technology in energy communities

namic and customized dynamic. Customized dynamic sharing consistently outperformed both static and default dynamic sharing, with savings ranging from 0.64% to 41.50%, depending on the scenario. Authors in [20] analyzed ex-ante and ex-post dynamic sharing with battery storage in residential self-consumption example in Spain. An ex-ante allocation introduces significant uncertainty, making it inadvisable unless based on historical data. While a dynamic ex-post allocation could be optimized, its high computational complexity and implementation costs would ultimately impact billing. Ensuring fairness in energy communities is crucial to maintaining stability, but existing game-theoretic methods are computationally intensive and difficult to scale. The paper [21] proposes a novel method that enables real-time energy sharing based on individual contributions, balancing fairness and efficiency while significantly reducing computation time, making it practical for large communities. The work [22] schedules uninterruptible shiftable devices for maximizing self-consumption in a shared PV system and compares centralized (CP) and partially distributed (PDP) approaches. While PDP significantly outperforms CP in computational efficiency, it maintains high solution quality, with only a slight deviation from optimality and a cost increase of under 17.5% due to grid imports.

Some papers of the literature that focus on the benefits of local energy sharing are described in Table 2.

Table 2: Local energy sharing

Reference	Focus of the paper	Conclusion
[23]	An optimal network charge mechanism for prosumers in P2P trading	The network charge mechanism is favorable ensuring benefits for the grid operator and prosumers; energy storage (ES) will make the prosumers more sensitive to the network charge price changes and impact the P2P market

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Table 2 (continued)

Reference	Focus of the paper	Conclusion
[24]	Comparison of individual and collective energy management in the energy community	Prosumers in the energy community achieve lower electricity costs compared to the case with individual energy management, except for FiT. If the final user does not own ES but is self-sufficient on a high level, it is more profitable not to join the community
[25]	Decentralized P2P energy trading market based on blockchain technology without the involvement of a third party	Hybrid P2P energy trading significantly reduces peak electricity demand from the main grid, more beneficial local prices for energy trading resulting in 2.5 years initial investment in PV return
[26]	Multi-energy sharing methodology for a gas-electricity integrated energy system	Fairness and equal satisfaction are ensured by balancing the utility and expenses of the energy hubs involved in the P2P trading, optimal energy sharing strategy improves social welfare
[27]	P2P trading within a blockchain-driven local energy market with a shared energy storage system	Users reduced a portion of their electricity costs, while imports, and exports were minimized, and the profitability of suppliers and operators was maintained
[28]	Bilateral trade preferences on the energy prices and volume	Hyperledger blockchain ensures reliability and customizability, allowing for flexible bilateral trading strategies while maximizing user autonomy, reducing household energy costs and overall energy imports from the main grid, increasing efficiency

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Table 2 (continued)

Reference	Focus of the paper	Conclusion
[29]	Influence of local P2P trading on network voltage	Voltage preserved within limits while significantly reducing prosumers' electricity bills and ensuring a fair and stable payoff distribution
[30]	A blockchain based P2P model for increasing trust among users and reducing default behavior	Waiting times and penalties used for discouraging default behavior and ensuring trading stability with reduced electricity costs
[31]	Reduction of the energy exchange between end-users and the supplier	Self-consumption improved by using the battery or cooperating with neighbors, reduction of energy costs, losses and unnecessary exchange of energy with the supplier
[32]	A P2P trading algorithm based on Stackelberg game, where sellers determine price and quantity, while buyers adjust their participation ratio	Proposed model incentivizes prosumers to support grid stability and provides a framework for utility companies to accommodate P2P trading in monopolistic energy markets

1.1.2. *Lessons learned from real-world implementation in pilot projects*

The community energy sector in Italy has been investigated in [33] reviewing community energy initiatives with the focus on three case studies: Retenergie and E'nostra, WeForGreen, and Energia Positiva. The work discussed in the paper concludes that community energy is still at a niche level, i.e. mainly small programs highly dependent on national PV incentives. However, the three companies mentioned above made a step forward and started the projects on a national level creating opportunities for final consumers to install in RES. Community cooperatives (CC) are investigated in [34] for enhancing the development and implementation of REC through CC in Italy. First of all, the paper points out the main weakness related to CC, such as the absence of a clear legal framework and national register of

CCs which will clearly define CC with the same characteristics on the national level fostering their development. The paper concludes that although some differences between REC and CC are noted (the most important one is that REC is used for producing energy from RES, unlike CC which can be used for different activities), many similar features are discovered which will contribute to the development of both forms.

The project Compile [35] focuses on the transition from a centralized power system to flexible and secure decentralized local systems through the creation, integration, and optimal operation of energy communities which have a positive effect on the local economy and social welfare. The project has five pilot sites: Luče in Slovenia, Križevci in Croatia, Rafina in Greece, Lisbon in Portugal, and Crevillent in Spain. The project developed 6 tools focused on energy community management and operation. The first energy cooperative in Portugal was established in August 2022 in the Civil Parish of Vila Boa do Bispo. The main goal is the promotion of RES, improving self-consumption in the community and self-sufficiency. Self Consumption Community was created in Lugaggia in order to unite ten houses and PV production from the local kindergarten [36]. Two novel technical solutions were provided to final users. In the first one, a centralized energy management platform is used with a smart meter for sensing and actuation. In the second solution, a decentralized control approach is secured by blockchain technology. The project RE/SOURCED is focused on the integration of a medium-sized and self-sufficient energy system in Transfo, Belgium [37]. All citizens will participate in the energy community cooperating through shared infrastructure. A legal entity was established as defined in the EU directives to demonstrate the results of the proposed EU policy. The results show that this approach, due to some legislative requirements and limitations, does not bring the highest benefits to all members. The main objective of the project SCCALE 20-30-50 is to build more than 26 energy communities based on the proposed methodology which will be tested and validated in 5 pilots: Parentium (Croatia), Licht Leuven (Belgium), Buurtwarmte (The Netherlands), Les Économes (France), Hyperion II (Greece) [38]. Each pilot location is chosen to demonstrate different low-carbon solutions: district heating deployment, cultural heritage public building renovation, CSC schemes, improving energy efficiency and collective purchasing, the PV system, and sustainable heating. The pilots are focused on developing simple, understandable, and practical approaches that will increase local citizen engagement and their participation in the clean energy transition. Citizens will be able to invest

in public projects, such as PV systems and heat pumps. The main idea of the project WiseGRID is to develop technologies that will increase the smartness, stability, and security of an open, consumer-centric European energy grid based [39]. Demand response (DR) programs, advanced monitoring and operation of the distribution grid, smart integration of electric vehicles (EV) and RES, and other low-carbon technologies will enhance the market participation of cooperatives. Five pilot sites are developed in the project: Ghent in Belgium, Crevillent in Spain, Terni in Italy, Kythnos, and Mesogia in Greece.

Platform Cleanwatts [40] developed a behind-the-meter energy management system for each community member, while participating in energy and flexibility markets by optimally controlling generation, consumption, and storage in the community. Several modules are developed in the platform, while Kiplo® Energy Communities enables the optimization of renewable energy communities and peer-to-peer trading within a community. Results show that community members were able to purchase clean energy which is around 30 % cheaper than their normal bills. Finally, with the initiative was able to reach 44% carbon neutrality, saving approximately 19 tons of CO2 in a single year. Powerledger platform [41] developed the local energy market for P2P trading. Each participant gains benefits from local energy exchange. Locational pricing results in increased grid utilization, while energy exchange reduces curtailment and the need for flexibility [42].

The results of these projects are summarized in the Table 3:

1.2. Identified good practices in the EU member states suitable for integration in Croatia

Austria developed an information platform [43] for energy communities where practical examples can be found, while community members can learn about decentralized energy generation systems, gather information on business models and tools, and download useful templates for different administrative procedures. Static and dynamic KoR are defined. With static KoR, each member of the community is allocated a pre-agreed fixed share of generated electricity. With dynamic KoR, the generated electricity is divided according to the members' consumption behavior. Static KoR are easy to understand and traceable for the individual members. Dynamic KoR are more difficult to understand but are generally more economical due to the optimized distribution of the generated electricity. We observed electricity

Table 3: Conclusions and results of the projects

Reference	Project / Pilot sites / Countries	Results and lessons learned
[33]	Italy - Retenergie and E'nostra, WeForGreen, and Energia Positiva	Small programs highly dependent on national PV incentives
[35]	Compile – Slovenia, Croatia, Greece, Portugal, Spain	Optimal integration and control of all energy vectors in energy communities achieved through developed tools
[36]	Self-consumption community Lugaggia, Italy	Successful testing of centralized energy management platforms and decentralized control with blockchain technology
[37]	RE/SOURCED project, Transfo, Belgium	Due to extensive legislative requirements and limitations, participation of citizens in energy communities does not bring the highest benefits to all members
[38]	SCCALE 20-30-50-Croatia, The Netherlands, Greece, France, Belgium	Development of simple, understandable, and practical approaches that will increase local citizen engagement and their participation in the clean energy transition
[39]	WiseGRID – Belgium, Spain, Italy, Greece, Austria	Enhance the market participation of cooperatives with demand response programs and advanced monitoring
[40]	Cleanwatts	Clean energy 30 % cheaper compared to normal bills, Finally, 44% carbon neutrality
[41]	Powerledger	Benefits for participants involved in p2p trading, reduction of load curtailment

tariffs for local use, and a static and dynamic energy distribution scheme, as an example of best practice in Austria, was applied to the Croatian model.

The overview of the regulatory framework for collective self-consumers, RECs, and CESs in the EU member states is detected from [44], [45], [46].

In order to promote citizens' actions and incentives for the energy community, the regulatory framework should adequately stimulate PV integration and energy sharing without unnecessary limitations, and extensive and unclear administration.

The law in Croatia defines that the energy community should deliver to the DSO the following list of measuring points: a list of production units in the community, storage units, community members, and KoR applied for energy sharing. All these measuring points must be equipped with smart meters. However, the regulation in France and Luxembourg requires a more detailed contract between the DSO and energy community representatives or collective self-consumers containing the energy sharing methodology and sharing coefficients (keys) based on either the consumption profile of final customers or investment share. Together with a fixed coefficient for energy sharing (also called a static key), Spain proposed the use of variable coefficients (dynamic key) defined for each hour, accepted by all members, and delivered to the DSO. The value of the coefficients can be determined based on the energy requirements, the economic contribution in the generation installation, or any other criterion. On the contrary, in Austria dynamic KoR for energy sharing are not defined in advance because the produced energy is smartly shared between all community members in order to increase local self-consumption.

Three KoR are available in France [47] : fixed allocation keys, variable (or dynamic) allocation keys, and variable allocation keys according to a rule. The energy flow produced by the collective self-consumption operation is subject to the different tariffs and taxes on electricity: value added tax (VAT), contribution to the public electricity service (CSPE) and tariff for the use of the public electricity network (TURPE). There are more than 700 collective-self consumptions in France, involving 8500 participants. Variable allocation keys according to a rule consistently outperformed both static and default dynamic sharing, with savings ranging from 0.64% to 41.50%, depending on the scenario. In July 2023 the Brussels municipality of Ixelles established an energy community called "Courant Alternatif" involving three municipality buildings. Surplus electricity produced by the solar panels and not consumed within community is shared with 14 local residents and a company at

a lower price (€0.18/kWh compared to the traditional €0.30/kWh), making renewable energy accessible to those unable to install solar panels by themselves [48]. The LEF initiative in the Netherlands involves approximately 15 homeowners who generate their own electricity for self-consumption and exchange within the community with blockchain transactions aiming to make the community predominantly self-sufficient and alleviate pressure on the power grid [49]. Feldheim in Germany operates a local grid powered by 55 wind turbines with a capacity of 125.1 MW, a solar park, and a biogas plant utilizing livestock slurry and energy crops. Residents benefit from electricity prices lower than the national average, showcasing a successful model of local energy autonomy [50].

Described examples confirm well-defined regulatory frameworks supporting energy sharing and cooperatives. Grid access and financial incentives, such as reduction in grid charges for shared energy encourage participation in community projects. Moreover, many large-scale examples of energy community and self-consumption projects exist, and the number is still increasing. Advanced smart grids, blockchain-based energy trading, and integrated battery storage support self-consumption. On the other hand, regulation in Croatia is complex and discourages small consumers from joining energy communities due to high costs, unclear procedures, and lengthy approval processes, such as registration of energy community costing 1 000 euros, restrictions on net-metering and no grid fee reductions. There are only 4 established energy communities in Croatia, however they are still not in operation because the DSO has not yet prepared their systems for energy sharing procedures. Blockchain technology and battery systems for energy sharing in Croatia are not even considered in the theoretical examples and studies. In the observed examples citizens play an active role in managing energy production, with strong cooperative networks and local decision-making, while in Croatia awareness of local energy initiatives was growing, but citizens are slowly losing the interest due to unchanged situation for several years.

Even though the regulation in Croatia requires that the contract contains the key applied for the energy sharing, some obscurities regarding the excess of energy after the agreed sharing remain unanswered.

One of the main concerns is what difficulties DSO would face if community members had different suppliers. Sweden made a simple solution to this problem. The whole apartment building shares an electricity contract with the utility, while electricity consumption is also measured internally by the housing company affecting the monthly rent because each apartment can

freely choose their supplier. On the other hand, in Belgium is necessary that all community members have the same supplier. This is not the case for Croatia, community members can sign a contract with different suppliers.

When it comes to incentives for energy communities, some countries have implemented very attractive solutions. Austria gives a deduction of higher voltage level network charges for community members, Italy reduces network loss charges, while in Spain shared energy is considered self-consumed energy without any grid fees, tax, or levies. On the other hand, policy regulation in Flanders bans selling energy to other community members. This should be avoided. However, the regulatory framework in Ireland allows energy sharing and trading within the community which should be regular practice due to increased benefits for all members involved in energy exchange. Different benefits for energy sharing in Croatia are analyzed in the paper in order to provide insight into possible measures that will attract more consumers in local investments.

In Italy all members of the energy community must be located within the same area, specifically under the same primary substation that supplies that area [51], which drastically reduces the energy-sharing potential. On the other hand, a 2 km or 20 km diameter for energy sharing is used in France, while in Germany community members can be even up to 100 km away from each other. Croatian regulation recently abandoned geographical limitations.

When it comes to balancing responsibilities, there is no regulation or policy recommendation in Croatia. Final customers with RES production do not need to pay incentives for RES, however, this is still not defined for energy communities. The cost-benefit analysis conducted in this research will also include RES incentives.

It is interesting to notice that the project RE/SOURCED faced some challenges regarding legislation which limits the community members to achieve the highest social welfare when the energy community is defined as a legal entity. Croatian law also defines the citizen and renewable energy community as a legal entity. This can be seen as a burden in involving citizens in energy projects due to unclear requirements for energy communities and complicated administrative procedures.

1.3. Gaps and contributions

In line with the discussed literature review, the research focuses on legal and regulatory shortcomings that inhibit the broader acceptance and consumers' willingness to participate in energy-sharing projects in Croatia.

The knowledge gaps identified in the paper are the following:

- The literature lacks the energy management in the community after the energy sharing based on a specific key is applied, whether the energy surplus is shared between members of CSC who have larger consumption, or it is assumed that this energy is sold to the supplier.
- If the energy surplus is shared among community members, the literature does not answer if it is shared for free (as the primary purpose of energy community is not profit generation) or an internal trading pricing mechanism is determined.
- Previously published papers do not specify the most suitable metering approach for different types of final customers in CSC and the community.
- There is a lack of studies examining how different end user types (households vs. businesses) with unique energy consumption patterns and pricing structures impact energy sharing mechanisms and overall community profitability.

The paper investigates knowledge gaps in energy surplus management and the impact of different energy-sharing keys. Using 15-minute and monthly net metering, the study compares effects on electricity bills savings and community profitability. The paper compares two-tier energy distribution, where surplus is either sold to the suppliers or shared among other community members with high consumption. Financial analyses of free and priced energy sharing are compared. Various net metering strategies are evaluated for households and businesses, showing that mixed-user communities achieve greater financial benefits.

Based on the revised literature review and regulatory frameworks in European countries, the authors propose the following contributions:

- The paper proposes a selection mechanism of the most beneficial net-metering approach for different types of energy communities based on the realistic cost reduction analyses and return of investment calculations.
- Detailed financial analyses of collective self-consumption in Croatia based on different coefficients for energy sharing (KoR) and net-metering

approaches are conducted. This not only enhances the understanding of net-metering strategies in Croatia but also provides practical insights for optimizing energy sharing key and reflecting costs to individual members within diverse community structures.

- This work investigates how potential options affect individual electricity bill reduction if excess PV production occurs after KoR have already been applied in case energy is shared for free between community members and energy is charged at the internally defined price.
- Based on several cost-benefits analyses and return of investment calculations for different types of energy communities, this work proposes an innovative type of energy community composed of a household with their own PV generation and a business customer with significant differences in prices set by the supplier resulting in the most favorable energy sharing price. This analysis underscores the economic benefits of including diverse user types in energy communities, ultimately enhancing their overall profitability and sustainability.
- In order to broaden the acceptance of local RES investments, the paper suggests RES incentive deduction and network charges reduction for energy shared between community members supported by diverse energy cost analyses in local energy-sharing projects.

1.4. Paper organization

Section 2 analyzes the profitability of investment in PV for individual consumers and business consumers, Section 3 for library-kindergarten energy community and household-kindergarten energy community, and Section 4 for collective-self consumption. Section 5 finalizes and concludes the paper.

2. Case studies and analyzes

Based on the reviewed literature, it was concluded that all models heavily depend on the incentivizing financial structure, which has become our primary focus. The literature emphasizes the importance of comparing individual prosumer models with their participation in energy communities or collective energy-sharing models. Several articles identify the challenge of distributing excess energy that cannot be immediately consumed among

community members lacking battery storage. We examined a so-called two-tier distribution of electricity and its impact on the overall profitability of investment returns and the savings achieved by members. Inspired by research demonstrating the connection between loss reduction, decreased energy exchange with suppliers, and reduced need for transmission through local energy sharing, we modelled the impact of reducing grid fees for locally consumed energy generated from the community's own resources or through collective sharing. Based on the discussed regulatory frameworks from different EU countries, this research calculates the cost of individual final customers and members of the energy community including diverse policies in order to define which ones are the most beneficial for their implementation.

In Croatia, two types of final customers with their own electricity generation are distinguished:

- **Final customer in self-supply category** is a household with monthly net metering. Prices are set by the supplier and known in advance.
- **Final customer with own electricity generation** is a business customer or a household with 15-minute net metering, while the selling prices are determined on a monthly basis as a ratio between the total cost of purchased energy and the total amount of purchased energy (for further explanation see Section 2.2).

Monthly net metering allows for the unused generated energy, which accumulates throughout the month, to be deducted from consumption at the end of the month, with the grid acting as a virtual storage. In 15-minute net metering, the unused generated energy is deducted in each 15-minute interval, and at the end of the month, it is converted into a monetary credit.

Multiple simulations are run to demonstrate the effect of these policy requirements on the energy community in Croatia based on realistic measurement data extracted from the Croatian Distribution System Operator (DSO) database:

- with and without financial remuneration for shared energy,
- different types of net metering (15-minute interval and monthly basis),
- deduction or reduction of some electricity bill components - RES incentives, transmission network charges, distribution network charges,

- different types of community members - only households, only business customers, and a household-business customer energy community.

The cost of managing the energy community has not been considered in this paper, however, in Croatia, it is necessary to have a fully employed person for this role. Different cost assets were applied in the calculations for solar photovoltaic systems, reflecting the size of the installations: 1.480,00 €/kW for residential systems, 1.300,00 €/kW for library installations, and 1.040,00 €/kW for business customers, which were used to determine the return on investment time discussed in the paper. The payback period was determined using the following formula:

$$PP = \frac{I}{S} \quad (1)$$

where:

- PP is the payback period (years),
- I is the total investment cost (€),
- S is the annual savings achieved by installing the PV system alone or both installing the PV system and participating in the energy community, depending on the specific scenario analyzed (€).

The achieved annual savings were calculated as:

$$S = C_{\text{before}} - C_{\text{after}} \quad (2)$$

where:

- C_{before} represents the total electricity cost before PV installation and/or participation in the energy community,
- C_{after} represents the total electricity cost after PV installation and/or participation in the energy community.

Different types of energy communities were examined, including their specific characteristics related to consumption, production, and electricity pricing. All consumption data were obtained from the Croatian DSO and analyzed using MS Excel and Python. Based on real data, the research

modelled the energy-sharing key and simulated energy distribution among community members. All results (empirical) and conclusions (theoretical) were obtained through calculations based on the collected data. The empirical results from the case studies are focused on analysing energy-sharing mechanisms and their effectiveness in various community configurations. The literature review provided examples of best practices and contextual insights while identifying knowledge gaps relevant to energy-sharing projects. The theoretical contributions were drawn in the conclusion based on the calculations and modelling conducted in the paper. By integrating these empirical results with the insights gained from the literature review and upgraded in our paper, the research offers a comprehensive understanding of the dynamics of energy communities in Croatia.

2.1. Individual household

The first subsection starts from the individual household level to demonstrate how prices are calculated based on different types of net metering. The research investigates the profitability of investment in a PV system in a Croatian household located in Zagreb based on the load measurement data collected from Croatian DSO and PV production data from [52]. The monthly cost for a household in a self-supply category with monthly net metering is calculated as shown in Table 4. The household has a two-tariff pricing option: high-tariff (HT) during the day, and low-tariff (LT) during the night. The energy prices are defined by Croatian supplier HEP Elektra, while network charges by Croatian ODS (HEP DSO) and TSO (HOPS), [53] and [54]. Prosumers do not pay VAT for excess generation injected into the grid.

According to Croatian legislation, self-supply customers settle the difference between consumed and produced electricity at the end of each month. If they produce more than they consume, the surplus is sold to the supplier, while they receive compensation from the supplier, equal to 80% of the purchase price excluding grid fees and other charges. On the other hand, if they consume more than they produce, they need to buy energy from the supplier and pay the supply price along with fees for renewable energy sources and grid charges. For high tariff (HT), at the end of the month, the customer consumed 550 kWh but produced 1,500 kWh, meaning 950 kWh of surplus was sold to the supplier. The supplier buys this surplus at a rate of 0.06 €/kWh, generating 57.00 € in revenue for the customer. For low tariff (LT), the customer consumed 400 kWh and produced 80 kWh, so they must pay for the 320 kWh withdrawn from the grid. The cost is 0.039 €/kWh (12.48

Table 4: Methodology for monthly electricity bill calculation for self-supply customer

Description	Energy balance kWh	Cost €
HT 0.079 €/kWh for purchasing, 0.06 €/kWh for selling	-950	-57.00
LT 0.039 €/kWh for purchasing, 0.03 for selling €/kWh	320	12.48
HT consumption kWh	550	
LT consumption kWh	400	
HT production kWh	1500	
LT production kWh	80	
RES incentives 0.014 €/kWh	320	4.48
Supply charge 0.98€/month	1	0.98
Total 1		-39.06
HT network charges 0.052 €/kWh	-950	0
LT network charges 0.022 €/kWh	320	7.04
Measurement charge 1.33 €/month	1	1.33
Total 2		8.37
After tax	13%	9.46
Monthly bill €	Total 1 + After tax	-29.60

€), plus a renewable energy fee of 4.48 € and a grid charge of 7.04 €. Additionally, fixed monthly charges apply: 1.33 € for the measurement charge and 0.98 € for supply charge. 13% VAT is applied only to expenses, not to the energy sold, adding 1.09 € in costs. A negative balance means the supplier owes the customer 29.60 € due to the surplus energy produced.

Similar procedure is applied with flat price option, where instead of HT and LT, only one tariff occurs, and the calculation is based on the difference between consumption and production within this single tariff. Figure 1 compares the annual electricity cost for a household in Zagreb with and without an installed 2.5 kW PV system, under flat and two-tariff pricing options. The results clearly demonstrate the significant cost reduction achieved with PV integration in both cases, with savings of 62.4% in the flat tariff and 65% in the two-tariff option. Return on investment for this PV size is less than 9 years for both cases (8.76 years for the two-tariff option and 8.62 years for the flat tariff). The impact of the pricing model on savings ultimately depends on the household's consumption profile, as different usage patterns influence the distribution of self-consumed and exported energy. However, since both cases follow a net metering approach, they yield comparable payback periods,

reinforcing the financial viability of PV investment regardless of the chosen tariff structure. Furthermore, to achieve the highest benefits, net metering should be monthly based, not based on 15-minute time intervals.

Figure 1: Comparison of annual electricity costs in flat and two-tariff pricing without and with PV system

2.2. Business customer in Zagreb

The business customer analysed in the research is categorized as a final customer with their own production with 15-minute net metering. The prices for buying energy are agreed with the supplier, while the prices for selling energy to the supplier are calculated on a monthly basis, following the methodology defined by the Renewable Energy Sources and High-Efficiency Cogeneration Act [55], as shown in (3):

$$\lambda^{PV} = 0.9 \cdot \frac{\lambda^{HT} \cdot E^{HT} + \lambda^{LT} \cdot E^{LT}}{E^{HT} + E^{LT}} = \frac{0.061 \cdot 1200 + 0.034 \cdot 1500}{1200 + 1500} = 0.041 \text{€}/\text{kWh} \quad (3)$$

λ^{PV} is the calculated monthly price for energy injection in the grid, based on the weighted average of the high-tariff and low-tariff electricity prices. The formula considers the proportion of energy consumed in each tariff period to determine a representative price for injected energy. λ^{HT} is HT electricity price (excluding other charges), λ^{LT} is LT electricity price (excluding other charges), E^{HT} is the total monthly amount of consumed energy in HT (in kWh), E^{LT} is the total monthly amount of consumed energy in LT (in kWh).

The formula applies a regulatory factor of 0.9, which reduces the final compensation rate for surplus energy injected into the grid. This mechanism ensures that prosumers do not build oversized power plants solely for selling electricity to the grid, aligning with regulatory goals to promote self-consumption rather than large-scale surplus production. The specific price calculated in this case is based on the data provided in Table 5.

Table 5 demonstrates the monthly cost calculation for the final customer with their own electricity generation.

Table 5: Methodology for monthly electricity bill calculation for final customer with own electricity generation

Description	Energy balance kWh	Cost €
HT 0.061 €/kWh for purchasing	1200	73.2
LT 0.034 €/kWh for purchasing €/kWh	1500	51
Excess production 0.041 €/kWh	-3100	-127.1
RES incentives 0.014 €/kWh	2700	37.8
Charge for business customer 0.0005€/kWh	2700	1.35
Total		36.25
Peak power charge 3.45 €/kW	30	103.5
HT network charges 0.028 €/kWh	1200	33.6
LT network charges 0.022 €/kWh	1500	33
Measurement charge 8.8 €/month	1	8.8
Total		215.15
After tax	13%	279.70

This calculation differs from the self-consumption model, as netting is not based on the difference between the monthly cumulative production and consumption. Instead, production and consumption are accounted for separately, with the final amount obtained by deducting monetary values rather than energy quantities, and the energy balance is calculated based on 15-minute intervals recorded by smart meters.

The table provides a detailed breakdown of various cost components. The purchase of electricity under HT and LT tariffs is shown with the corresponding costs, while excess production is valued at a lower price calculated in (3), resulting in a negative amount (i.e., a reduction in total costs). It also includes incentives for renewable energy sources (RES) and an additional charge for business customers.

In addition to basic energy costs, network charges and fixed costs are also included, such as transmission and distribution fees, measurement costs, and the peak power charge, which is based on the highest 15-minute power demand measured during the billing period (month). This billing method is financially less favorable for customers with their own production, as it does not allow direct netting of consumed and produced energy, which could otherwise lead to significant savings. Instead, all financial components, both charges and credits, are summed and subtracted to calculate the final payable amount.

Based on collected PV and load measurement data together with the electricity prices for 2022 for this business customer, the period of investment return is shown in Table 6. It can be seen that with two-tariff pricing, the period of investment return in both 15-minute and monthly net metering is less than 10 years and shorter compared to flat pricing.

Although higher electricity prices make the installation of a solar power plant more cost-effective, the unfavorable billing method and the lower purchase price offered by the supplier extend the investment payback period compared to monthly net metering.

Table 6: Period of return of investment in years

net metering	Flat prices	Two-tariff pricing
15-minute	11.25	9.72
Monthly	10.57	9.04

3. Energy community

This study examines two energy community models, library-kindergarten and household-kindergarten, to explore how different participant compositions affect profitability. The library-kindergarten case involves two business entities operating under the same pricing structure, whereas the household-kindergarten case introduces a mix of residential and business consumers, where significant disparities in electricity pricing exist. The household buying price for HT/LT (€/kWh) is 0.079/0.039, while for businesses, it is 0.35/0.21. Comparing these models offers insights into how tariff structures and participant diversity influence the economic viability of energy sharing.

3.1. Library-kindergarten energy community

In the Croatian city Križevci local energy community was established. 30kW PV system was installed on the library rooftop [56]. Monthly consumption of library and kindergarten together with PV production are shown in Figure 2. It can be noticed that during the spring and summer months library has excess PV production which opens the door for energy sharing between the library and the kindergarten.

Figure 2: Monthly electricity consumption and production in Križevci energy community

The profitability of the PV system when the library is self-sufficient oriented (excess PV production injected to the grid), is compared with community energy sharing between the library and the kindergarten. Two realistic pricing options are investigated (flat prices and two-tariff pricing) in both 15-minute and monthly net metering approaches in order to investigate which one would be the most beneficial for energy community members. Table 7 lists 8 scenarios for the library, while Table 8 lists 8 scenarios for the kindergarten with a focus on different pricing components for shared energy.

Analyses were conducted for both 15-minute and monthly net metering, with flat-tariff and two-tariff pricing. For the library, two cases were considered: the standalone case, where the PV system does not participate in the community, and the energy community case, where excess production is shared with the kindergarten. For the kindergarten, scenarios were created in which it always pays for the energy price but does not pay for transmission costs because the transmission network is not used for energy sharing. Depending on the scenario, it either pays only the distribution fee for shared

Table 7: Description of scenarios for library

Scenario	Description
S1	15-minute net metering, flat prices, standalone case
S2	15-minute net metering, flat prices, energy community
S3	monthly net metering, flat prices, standalone case
S4	monthly net metering, flat prices, energy community
S5	15-minute net metering, two-tariff pricing, standalone case
S6	15-minute net metering, two-tariff pricing, energy community
S7	monthly net metering, two-tariff pricing, standalone case
S8	monthly net metering, two-tariff pricing, energy community

Table 8: Description of scenarios for kindergarten

Scenario	Description
V1	Flat prices, distribution network charges
V2	Two-tariff pricing, distribution network charges
V3	Flat prices, no additional charges
V4	Two-tariff pricing, no additional charges
V5	Flat prices, distribution network charges, RES incentives
V6	Two-tariff pricing, distribution network charges, RES incentives
V7	Flat prices, RES incentives
V8	Two-tariff pricing, RES incentives

energy from the community, pays no additional fees, pays both the distribution fee and the RES fee, or pays only the RES fee.

Annual electricity bill reduction for the library is shown in Table 9. It is interesting to notice that due to the recent extreme increase in electricity prices for business customers in Croatia, the annual electricity bill reduction is similar in standalone and energy community cases (for all observed scenarios excluding S7 and S8 is less than 1%). However, the analysis shows that if the library has a two-tariff pricing contract with a monthly net metering option, participation in local energy sharing reduces the cost by almost 6%, which implies that monthly net metering for business customer is more beneficial compared to 15-minute net metering (S8 compared to S7).

Table 9: Annual electricity bill reduction in % for library with installed PV system - standalone and community case

Scenario	Standalone case	Scenario	Energy community
S1	74.46	S2	75.08
S3	83.37	S4	83.76
S5	76.54	S6	77.37
S7	80.92	S8	86.10

On the other hand, as shown in Figure 3 in all analyzed cases, for the kindergarten (without its own electricity generation) is more profitable to have a 15-minute net metering option. The reason for this different cost reduction for community members with and without their own electricity production can be explained in Figure 4. The bars in the graph represent different net metering and pricing options, while colours show on the annual level the percentage of energy produced in the library which is consumed in the library (blue colour), produced energy which is shared with the kindergarten (orange colour), produced energy injected in the grid (grey colour), and energy supplied from the grid for the library (yellow colour). More energy is shared with the kindergarten in the 15-minute net metering (in flat pricing option 19% compared to 12% in the monthly net metering, in HT 16% compared to the 15% in the monthly net metering, and in LT 3% compared to the 1% in monthly net metering). This results in lower electricity costs for the kindergarten because shared energy is supplied at a lower cost compared to the price set by the supplier. However, more energy is self-consumed in the library with the monthly net metering option (in flat pricing option 88%

compared to 56%, in HT 70% compared to the 47%, and in LT 15% compared to the 9% in 15-minute net metering) which results in lower electricity cost for the library in monthly net metering. In the 15-minute net metering approach, more energy is shared with the kindergarten. In the monthly net metering, the total injected and supplied energy is calculated at the end of the month as described in Table 4. At the end of the month, the amount of total consumption is compared to the amount of total production in each tariff. If the total production is higher than the total consumption in a specific tariff, the value of excess production is assumed to be shared with the kindergarten (this monthly financial calculation does not follow physical energy balance in real-time). This implies that more energy is self-consumed in the library under monthly net metering. On the other hand, in the 15-minute net metering, energy is balanced in each 15-minute time period. If excess production in the library occurs, it is assumed in the calculation that this excess is shared with the kindergarten. In this approach, more energy is shared with the kindergarten reducing the electricity bill due to lower prices for shared energy compared to the supplier price. The price for energy sharing is set as the mean value of the price set by the supplier for buying and selling energy. This price is lower than the buying price and at the same time higher than the selling price which implies more beneficial energy trading within the community. This price can have any value between the buying price and the selling price set by the supplier to result in profitable energy community trading.

Figure 3: Kindergarten’s annual electricity bill reduction in energy community

Figure 4: Annual energy flow in library-kindergarten energy community

When it comes to the profitability of forming an energy community composed of the same type of customers, such as two business customers described above, it can be noticed from Table 10 that in all analyzed scenarios the return of investment period is low (less than 3 years) without significant difference between library in the standalone case and community trading. From an exclusively financial point of view of the library, the profitability of forming an energy community remains questionable. However, as the main idea behind the energy community is not achieving a sole profit, some other aspects should also be included. The energy community is focused on achieving social, financial, and environmental benefits for all members, which is achieved with this type of trading.

3.2. Household-kindergarten energy community

In the energy community with various types of final customers, such as a household with installed PV and a kindergarten, different net-metering approaches and pricing options are applied for each customer. In this type of community trading price for energy sharing between community members can be more favorable (compared to the energy community with only households

Table 10: Period of investment return in the library-kindergarten community

Scenario	Years
S1	2.71
S2	2.68
S3	2.50
S4	2.48
S5	2.51
S6	2.52
S7	2.42
S8	2.29

or only business customers) due to the large difference in electricity prices for households and business customer in Croatia. To demonstrate this favorable price, Table 11 compares buying and selling prices set by the supplier together with prices for energy sharing in different types of energy communities. The energy-sharing prices are set as the mean value between buying and selling prices set by the supplier to ensure a fair cost-benefit distribution among participants. This approach lowers costs for consumers while providing producers with a better price than selling surplus energy to the supplier. By maintaining balance between both groups, it enhances the attractiveness and financial sustainability of energy sharing within the community.

Table 11: Buying and selling prices and energy sharing prices

Type of community	Buying price HT/LT €/kWh	Selling price HT/LT €/kWh	Energy sharing price HT/LT €/kWh
Only households	0.079/0.039	0.06/0.03	0.07/0.035
Only business customers	0.35/0.21	0.28/0.16	0.32/0.19
Household and business customer	0.079/0.039 0.35/0.21	0.06/0.03 0.28/0.16	0.21/0.12

It can be seen that the kindergarten, as a business customer, can trade energy with a household at a significantly lower rate compared to the supplier price (40% lower price). At the same time, this price is also beneficial for a

household (if compared with a selling price set by the supplier, a household with community trading can achieve even 3.5 times higher price). Table 12 compares the household’s savings in the annual electricity bill with the investment in PV in a standalone case and in the energy community. Scenarios for household are the same as for the library, and are described in Table 7. The household achieves more savings in a standalone case in the monthly net metering approach compared to 15-minute net metering due to more self-consumed energy. On the other hand, when they join the energy community, 15-minute net metering is more beneficial for both parties (higher cost reductions for households 66% compared to 65% in flat prices option and 80% compared to 77% in two-tariff pricing). The lowest period of investment return as shown in Table 13 is achieved in scenario S6 with two-tariff pricing in the energy community under 15-minute net metering approach because the energy not used in the household is shared with the kindergarten at the price of 3.5 higher compared to the price set by the supplier.

Table 12: Annual electricity bill reduction in % for household with installed PV system - standalone and community case with kindergarten

Scenario	Standalone case	Scenario	Energy community
S1	44.67	S2	66.52
S3	62.56	S4	65.08
S5	50.83	S6	80.76
S7	69.30	S8	77.15

Table 13: Period of investment return for household-kindergarten community

Scenario	Years
S1	12.04
S2	8.09
S3	8.60
S4	8.26
S5	11.21
S6	7.06
S7	8.22
S8	7.39

The kindergarten achieves significant annual electricity bill reduction

when participating in the energy community as shown in Figure 5. These savings are higher in the 15-minute net metering option due to more shared energy between community members. The kindergarten receives 199kWh from community PV with monthly net metering under flat prices and 1729 kWh with 15-minute net metering. Under two-tariff pricing, the same amount is shared in the monthly net metering and 509 kWh with 15-minute net metering. The highest savings are achieved in scenario V4 in which the kindergarten does not need to pay any additional charges for the shared energy, such as distribution and transmission network charges and RES incentives. However, it is interesting to compare scenarios V2 and V4. Unlike in scenario V4, in scenario V2 the kindergarten pays the distribution charge for the shared energy, however does not pay RES incentives. The annual savings are high in both cases which implies that this can serve as a basis for recommendation for a policy regulation for energy communities. Community members should be excepted from paying RES incentives for shared energy because energy is produced from RES. Removing the distribution network fee for shared energy significantly increases the benefits of energy communities and encourages large-scale deployment.

Figure 5: Annual electricity bill savings for kindergarten in energy community with household

4. Collective self-consumption

CSC can be defined as a group of at least two cooperating renewable self-consumers who are located in the same building or multi-apartment block. Measurement data from one distributed PV system and corresponding 10 consumption metering points (MP) were collected to demonstrate the energy and cash flow in the CSC approach.

Collective self-consumption members in Austria can choose between dynamic and static KoR. Static KoR are determined based on the agreement between community members and can be changed upon request only once per year. A similar approach was used in this work. Static KoR was defined as an equal proportion of produced energy to all members. On the other hand, dynamic KoR in Austria is defined for each 15-minute time interval and allocates energy optimally, i.e., based on the ratio of individual consumption to collective consumption. The term “dynamic” was used in this work following Austrian terminology, where it refers to allocation that changes over time, even if on a predefined schedule. In our case, dynamic KoR was defined on a monthly or annual basis, according to each member’s proportion of total collective consumption.

For the sake of comprehensiveness in conducting analyses, it was decided to investigate the costs and electricity consumption in 15-minute and monthly net metering options with three different KoR for energy sharing:

- static - all CSC members $, \forall n \in N$ receive the same amount of energy P_n^{PV} from PV production P^{prod} ,

$$P_n^{PV} = \frac{P^{prod}}{N}, \forall n \in N \quad (4)$$

- annual - defined once per year, CSC members share annual PV production P_a^{prod} based on the annual consumption ratio defined as a ratio between annual consumption of household n $P_{a,n}^{load}$ and collective amount of annual consumption defined as an annual sum of consumption of all members $\sum_{n=1}^N P_{a,n}^{load}$

$$P_{a,n}^{PV} = P_a^{prod} \cdot \frac{P_{a,n}^{load}}{\sum_{n=1}^N P_{a,n}^{load}}, \forall n \in N \quad (5)$$

- monthly - defined once per year, CSC members share monthly PV production P_m^{prod} based on the monthly consumption ratio defined as a ratio between monthly consumption of household n $P_{m,n}^{load}$ and collective amount of monthly consumption defined as an monthly sum of consumption of all members $\sum_{n=1}^N P_{m,n}^{load}$

$$P_{m,n}^{PV} = P_m^{prod} \cdot \frac{P_{m,n}^{load}}{\sum_{n=1}^N P_{m,n}^{load}}, \forall n \in N \quad (6)$$

Figure 6 shows annual consumption for each MP and the shared energy from the PV system based on the static, annual, and monthly KoR . The authors do not have any information explaining the low consumption profile for MP5, MP6, MP8, and MP9, however, it is assumed that all MPs invested in the local PV system and have the right to use the generated energy. Different assumptions are also possible, however, they are out of the scope of this research .

Figure 6: Annual electricity consumption and shared energy with static, annual and monthly keys

Authors noticed one very interesting fact about excess energy sharing which was not mentioned nor answered before in the scientific research and regulation. This fact is an open question about the energy from the PV system after a specific type of KoR for energy sharing is applied: what happens with the excess energy after the energy sharing is applied based on a specific KoR? Is that amount of energy shared between members of CSC who have larger consumption or it is assumed that this energy is injected into the grid? If it is shared in the second stage between CSC members, is that energy shared for free, or is an internal trading price determined?

In order to answer these questions, both 15-minute and monthly net metering cost calculations are developed for CSC members with excess energy based on different types of KoR.

The annual cost of CSC member n in a 15-minute net metering approach is calculated as a sum of a monthly cost as described with (7):

$$cost_n^{15min} = \sum_{m=1}^{12} cost_{n,m}^{15min} \quad (7)$$

Monthly cost is calculated as the sum of a cost (or profit) for each 15-minute time interval as described in (8) where T is equal to the total number of 15-minute intervals in the observed month. If a member has a deficit of energy (after the allocation of local production $P_{n,t}^{PV}$), the member pays a buying price for electricity. In case a member has excess energy, this energy can be shared for free between other community members, it can be sold to other members, or it can be sold to the supplier:

$$cost_{n,m}^{15min} = \sum_t^T \left\{ \begin{array}{l} (P_{n,t}^{load} - P_{n,t}^{PV}) \cdot \lambda^B, \text{ if } P_{n,t}^{load} - P_{n,t}^{PV} > 0 \\ (P_{n,t}^{load} - P_{n,t}^{PV}) \cdot \lambda^S, \text{ if } P_{n,t}^{load} - P_{n,t}^{PV} < 0 \end{array} \right. \quad (8)$$

$P_{n,t}^{load}$ is a consumption of a member n in time interval t , $P_{n,t}^{PV}$ is allocated PV production to a member n in a time interval t , while λ^B is a buying price composed of electricity charge, transmission and distribution network fee and RES incentive. λ^S is a selling price that can be equal to zero if energy is shared for free, or it can be agreed among members, or calculated as shown in (3) if it is sold to the supplier.

Annual cost of member n in monthly net metering is calculated as a sum of monthly costs described with (9):

$$cost_n^{net} = \sum_{m=1}^{12} cost_{n,m}^{monthly} \quad (9)$$

The monthly cost is calculated as described in (10). Total monthly consumption or withdrawn energy from the grid is reduced by the total amount of monthly allocated PV production from the local generation to member n . If a member has a deficit of energy (after the allocation of local production) on a monthly basis, the member pays a buying price for electricity. In case a member has excess energy, this energy can be shared for free between other community members, it can be sold to other members, or it can be sold to the supplier:

$$cost_{n,m}^{monthly} = \sum_{m=1}^{12} \begin{cases} (E_{n,m}^{load} - P_{n,m}^{PV}) \cdot \lambda^B, & \text{if } E_{n,m}^{load} - P_{n,m}^{PV} > 0 \\ (E_{n,m}^{load} - P_{n,m}^{PV}) \cdot \lambda^S, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

where $E_{n,m}^{load}$ is the total monthly consumption in month m of the community n , while $P_{n,m}^{PV}$ is a monthly amount of PV production allocated to the community member n in month m . λ^B is a buying price composed of electricity charge, transmission, and distribution network fee, RES incentive, and tax. In monthly net metering, the DSO calculates the amount of energy supplied by the supplier as a difference between total monthly consumption and allocated PV production to the community member. λ^S is a selling price that can be equal to zero if energy is shared for free, or it can be agreed among members, or determined by the supplier.

Figure 7 represents annual costs for each MP when this excess energy is shared for free. Authors can easily find the support behind this free sharing approach in the Bill Sharing Method (BSM) from the literature [57], [58] and [59]. The blue bars in the figure represent the annual cost of electricity in a scenario where each member of the energy community receives an equal share of solar power production, regardless of their actual consumption. For members whose consumption exceeds that share (MP1, MP2, MP7, and MP10), this model results in the highest costs, as they have to make up the difference by purchasing electricity from the grid. MP3 and MP4 consume less than their allocated share but do not make a profit — MP3 even feeds more energy into the grid than it takes from it, while MP4 ends up balanced. In contrast, MP5, MP6, MP8, and MP9 receive significantly more energy than

they consume and therefore make a profit. Although part of the surplus is shared for free within the community, the remaining excess must be sold to the supplier, since no other members are able to absorb such a large amount of energy within the 15-minute intervals.

The orange bars represent the distribution of solar production proportional to each community member's annual electricity consumption. This model ensures that, on a yearly basis, no member feeds more energy into the grid than they draw from it, which means that no one makes a profit. Compared to grey bars, where production is allocated based on monthly consumption, this model is less cost-effective for most members, except for MP7 and MP10. Although they have the highest annual consumption, their usage is significantly lower during the period of peak solar production (May to September), so they cannot fully utilize their allocated share, as their consumption does not coincide with the time of production. The surplus energy is therefore allocated to members like MP2, MP4, MP5, MP6, and MP9, who often cannot consume all of it and must feed the excess into the grid. Since there are no other members able to absorb that much energy within the 15-minute intervals, the surplus must be transferred to the supplier. Nevertheless, unlike the equal-share model (blue bars), no profit is generated. Table 14 shows how electricity cost changes for each MP if the excess energy is remunerated at the price defined as the mean value between the buying and selling price set by the supplier. MP5, MP6, MP8 and MP9 due to low consumption have increased profit from 45% to more than 76% with the static KoR when the excess energy is remunerated. MP2 and MP3 have reduced costs, while others face increased costs due to high consumption which is supplied by excess PV production from other CSC members. The question remains how often the DSOs would allow the changes in the dynamic KoR. To answer this question, simulations are run for monthly and annual KoR. It can be seen from Table 14 that smaller cost changes occur with annual and monthly KoR which implies that PV production divided according to these KoR is more suitable compared to the static KoR with equal production sharing. The amount of investment of each CSC member in the collective PV system should also be related to the KoR used in the PV production sharing.

When it comes to the monthly net metering approach, it can be seen in Figure 8 that costs with energy remuneration differ more compared to the 15-minute net metering. In the monthly net metering approach, each MP faces a lower cost because more PV production can be used within CSC. Final

Figure 7: Annual electricity bill with different sharing KoR without charge for excess energy in 15-minute net metering approach

Table 14: Reduction/increase of electricity bill in % when excess energy is remunerated in 15-minute net metering approach

Metering point	Static KoR	Annual KoR	Monthly KoR
MP1	5.28	-0.86	-0.67
MP2	-2.64	-0.96	-2.72
MP3	-33.77	0.27	-0.27
MP4	1.22	7.71	6.96
MP5	51.52	0.79	0.65
MP6	45.92	0.64	0.62
MP7	11.44	0.87	1.34
MP8	51.49	0.15	0.23
MP9	76.92	12.67	12.59
MP10	5.78	-2.49	-1.99

Figure 8: Annual electricity bill with different KoR without charge for excess energy in monthly net metering approach

users with excess PV production can share this energy with other members, instead of selling it to the supplier in the monthly settlement period. The highest cost reduction is seen with the MPs with the highest consumption, MP7 and MP8, because their energy deficit can be supplied at a lower cost compared to the price set by the supplier. If the annual electricity cost in monthly net metering in Figure 8 is compared with the cost in 15-minute net metering in Figure 7, it can be noticed that each final customer faces a lower electricity cost. This implies that participants in CSC should be final customers in a self-supply category with monthly net metering. Moreover, monthly net metering results in less energy sharing between CSC members in the settlement process because more energy is self-consumed at the individual level as shown in Figure 9. The exception is the static KoR in which all final customers receive the same amount of energy. With the static KoR, some final customers will have more energy excess compared to the monthly or annual KoR which will result in more shared energy and increased profit for MP5, MP6, MP8, and MP9 (even more than double) as shown in Table 15.

In contrast, the remaining members (MP1, MP2, MP4, MP7, and MP10) see an increase in annual costs, as they must pay for the additional energy received from the community. When production is distributed proportionally to annual consumption, MP7 and MP10 benefit from lower costs, since during low-consumption months (May–September), the surplus energy they feed into the community generates additional income. MP8 also sees a slight

cost reduction for the same reason, while others face higher costs because they buy more energy from the community than they have surplus to sell. Under monthly-based distribution, MP6 and MP10 reduce their costs by earning from surplus energy shared with others. Although MP10 is one of the highest consumers, it generates surplus in certain months. However, since the energy balance is calculated separately for high (HT) and low (LT) tariffs, any surplus produced in HT cannot be used to offset NT consumption and must be transferred to the community.

Table 15: Reduction/increase of electricity bill in % when excess energy is remunerated in monthly net metering approach

Metering point	Static KoR	Annual KoR	Monthly KoR
MP1	13.63	2.15	2.43
MP2	9.13	4.25	6.08
MP3	44.43	7.02	5.15
MP4	5.72	4.02	3.92
MP5	100.58	0.31	0.48
MP6	105.44	0.19	-0.06
MP7	13.28	-2.23	0.30
MP8	108.23	-1.16	0.12
MP9	120.43	12.24	2.85
MP10	9.61	-3.07	-5.33

5. Conclusions

To increase the engagement of final customers in the low-carbon transition, it is crucial to ensure adequate education which will broaden investing in local RES. Energy sharing is seen as a vital part of the decarbonization process which will enhance the environmental, economic, and social benefits of the local community. In line with this, the paper is focused on the development of the local energy-sharing concept with a focus on the Croatian perspective and can easily be applied to other countries with poor or non-defined regulatory frameworks for energy community empowerment.

The paper compares the existing regulatory framework in Croatia highlighting the shortcomings which should be replaced with some well-functioning European practices. Based on local energy-sharing models with realistic load

Figure 9: Excess energy shared between members on the annual level

and PV measurement data, the paper analyses different forms of prosumers, energy communities, and CSC. Multiple scenario analyses are performed to demonstrate the effect of distribution and transmission network charges, RES incentives, keys of repartition for energy sharing in energy communities, and CSC in both monthly and 15-minute net metering approaches.

Based on the cost reduction calculations for realistic customers in Croatia, it can be concluded that the preferable net-metering approach, together with the reduction of specific electricity bill charges, will attract more people to take part in local energy sharing. The most beneficial net-metering approach in the energy community is based on the tariff option design and the type of final customers involved in the community energy sharing. In this research three types of communities are distinguished: only households, only business customers, and a combination of household and business customers. Moreover, this work investigates the benefits of the RES incentives and network charges deduction for shared energy between community members to establish some innovative changes in the Croatian local energy-sharing framework.

The thorough real-life simulations run in this research can serve as a proposal for specific regulatory changes that will enhance local citizens' engagement in RES investments due to increased local benefits for all involved members. Some final remarks are highlighted:

- It is necessary to ensure that both standalone houses and apartments in multi-apartment buildings with installed PV systems have the same

and non-discriminatory conditions for the calculation of electricity bill, i.e., final customers in a household category who are part of the CSC should have a monthly net metering approach. For end users who do not participate in energy sharing, monthly net metering is more cost-effective because they can use the electricity grid as a virtual energy storage system.

- Deduction of RES incentives for shared energy should be employed. The electricity generated from rooftop PV systems installed on household or multiapartment buildings and shared between community members is produced from renewable energy sources. This implies that each consumed kWh of energy from the installed rooftop PV system should be exempted from incentives for RES which the final customer usually pays in Croatia (0.01574768 €/kWh with VAT included).
- Each energy community should have a free choice of energy net-metering calculation, i.e., either monthly or 15-minute net metering. The same electricity net-metering calculation should be applied to each community member. With two-tariff pricing, both household and business customers experience a faster payback period in both 15-minute and monthly net metering compared to flat tariff pricing.
- Local energy sharing between different types of final customers (household and business customer) should have 15-minute net metering. The analyses have shown that the 15-minute net metering approach is more beneficial for final customers who have significant differences in electricity prices. This implies that in the settlement period, more energy is shared between a household and a business customer, while the internal price for energy sharing is more beneficial compared to the prices offered by the supplier resulting in a significant cost decrease for both members of the energy community.
- Energy sharing coefficients (KoR) in CSC should not be static. Monthly or even hourly (15-minute) based KORs result in optimal energy sharing with more adequately allocated PV production to each CSC member. Establishing an effective sharing key is crucial for ensuring that all users benefit, at least by keeping their costs consistent with those prior to joining the community. The analysis indicates that a dynamic

sharing key better meets user needs and favors savings compared to a static key, which is important for dividing PV production effectively.

- Achieving a two-level energy distribution with the remaining excess is beneficial for members, as it allows them to allocate it effectively and reduce their costs rather than immediately returning it to the supplier. The term “remaining excess” does not refer to the energy fed into the grid. Rather, it denotes the surplus energy that remains within the collective self-consumption (CSC) group after the first stage of KoR distribution. This energy is initially allocated to specific members who, at that moment, cannot fully utilize it, but it can still be redistributed to others in the second stage of the KoR process. The priority should be maximizing local energy self-consumption within the community. Our contribution lies in proposing and analyzing this two-stage model, comparing surplus allocation within the CSC either free of charge or remunerated. By assessing the financial and operational impacts, we provide insight into how redistribution affects members’ cost savings while offering guidance for policymakers and community organizers in designing fair, efficient energy-sharing frameworks that enhance self-consumption and equitable distribution. While remuneration supports fairness, it should incentivize internal use with prices lower than the supplier’s rate.
- Reducing or eliminating network fees for shared energy significantly increases savings and profitability for energy communities, while also encouraging large-scale adoption. Additionally, it is important to investigate how local energy sharing reduces losses, which could help determine a proportional reduction in fees based on this contribution.

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